

HIGH TEMPERATURE JOINING OF FIBRE REINFORCED METALS

N. J. Lindsay, V. D. Scott.

(University of Bath, Bath, Avon, U.K.)

R. L. Trumper.

(Admiralty Research Establishment, Holton Heath, Poole, Dorset, U.K.)

INTRODUCTION.

The joining of fibre-reinforced metals (FRMs) gives rise to problems that preclude the use of more conventional metal joining methods which rely intrinsically on some degree of tolerated component damage. Mechanical fastening, for example, requires substrate drilling which for FRMs may necessitate expensive diamond tooling; welding involves melting and re-freezing processes which are undesirable due to the non-wetting nature of the fibres and the possibility of fibre/matrix reaction; conventional brazing may be prohibited when dealing with FRMs possessing a matrix with a low solidus temperature compared with the temperature attained in usual brazing operations. Fortunately, however, alternative joining methods may be considered. In low temperature environments structural adhesives may be used (1) whilst, where higher temperatures are involved, diffusion bonding (liquid or solid state) is a candidate (2,3). This paper focuses attention on the diffusion bonding of an Al-7.0 wt% Si-0.4 wt%Mg casting alloy reinforced with low modulus carbon fibres, the composite being produced by a low pressure liquid metal infiltration route.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diffusion bonding experiments were carried out on Al-7.0wt% Si-0.4wt% Mg alloy reinforced with carbon fibres and also on the unreinforced alloy. Prior to diffusion bonding, all specimen surfaces were first ground on SiC paper finishing on 1200 grit, followed by ultrasonic cleaning and degreasing in chlorinated hydrocarbon. All bonding experiments involved the use of interlayers consisting of copper or aluminium foils. The copper foils (20 μm thick) were cleaned in 10%_{v/v} H₂SO₄ followed by degreasing, whilst the aluminium foils (10 μm thick) were simply degreased. Specimens, with the interlayers inserted were then placed in between heated platens which were attached to a modified Instron testing machine. The machine cross-head was programmed to deliver 10% strain to the specimen and the entire stress versus time profile was recorded in each case. Bonding temperatures of 510°C, 525°C and 550°C were investigated, all $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

Figures 1a and 1b show the stress versus time profiles for matrix and for composite specimen respectively at a temperature of 525°C. Joint strengths were assessed in the single-lap shear mode using an Instron 1195 tensile-testing machine. Metallography involved progressive polishing of the specimen surface followed by optical microscopy (unetched condition). The polished samples were also examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Electron-probe microanalysis (EPMA) was carried out, using the EDS facility fitted to the SEM, in order to establish the chemical composition of any phases that formed. Quantitative EPMA data were obtained by applying a ZAF correction method (4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Unreinforced metal.

Figure 2 illustrates a sample bonded for 30 minutes at 510°C using a copper foil interlayer. A typical cast alloy structure, primary aluminium grains surrounded by an eutectic mixture of silicon and aluminium, can clearly be seen. At the bonded interface several layers are visible. The central layer was found by EPMA to consist of almost pure copper. On either side was an intermetallic whose composition was close to that of CuAl; note the crack running through one of these intermetallic layers, probably arising from stresses set up on cooling from the bonding temperature. Outside the CuAl phase were layers of CuAl₂ and beyond this the casting alloy itself with little diffused copper ($\approx 2.0\text{wt}\%$). There also seems to be evidence of some coarsening of the silicon phases in the vicinity of the bond line.

Figure 3 shows a specimen bonded for 60 minutes at 510°C. The layers of CuAl and CuAl₂ are still present, again with a crack confined to the CuAl layer. The band of pure copper that remained after bonding for 30 minutes at this temperature has been removed.

Fig 4 illustrates a sample bonded for 60 minutes at 525 °C: Although the bond line can just be seen no intermetallic layers are visible. It was also noted that some material had been extruded from the interface and deposited at the edge of the specimen. These observations indicate that at these temperatures a liquid eutectic (CuAl₂+Al) had formed during bonding which was expelled from the region of the joint. Thus the copper, by dilution with aluminium during the diffusion process, was progressively removed.

Carbon fibre reinforced metal.

A transverse section of the composite is shown in figure 5. The carbon fibres are uniform in diameter ($7.0\pm 0.5\mu\text{m}$) but are not uniformly distributed. This is not surprising in view of the fact that the carbon fibres were infiltrated as woven tows. Some clusters of fibres appear to be in contact with one another, with little if any metal separating them. The substantial modification to the cast eutectic structure caused by the carbon fibres is clearly revealed. The silicon particles are now more rod-like in shape.

Transverse sections of the composite were bonded at 525°C for 30 minutes, figure 6. It may seem at first sight surprising that the copper-rich material containing the low melting point eutectic has not now been extruded from the bond line, as had been noted in figure 4. It must be presumed, therefore, that the presence of the fibres has in some way impeded movement of the copper-rich material.

We propose the following explanation, which is consistent with the stress versus time data illustrated in figures 1a and 1b. In the case of unreinforced metal, a peak stress of ≈ 10 MPa occurred when a strain of 10% was applied. Thereafter the stress decreased rapidly, indicative of plastic flow and extrusion of low melting point eutectic material, cf figure 4. With the fibre reinforced system, figure 1b, the maximum stress developed at the joint was very much higher ≈ 105 MPa, and this level was sustained for the 30 minutes duration of the bonding experiment. Clearly, therefore, the fibres were supporting the load and little plastic deformation of the metal and only very limited movement of the low melting point eutectic was possible. Certainly, the copper was not progressively removed and this we attribute to, firstly, the more tortuous diffusion path caused by the presence of the fibres in the metal and, secondly, the lack of any squeezing action which ejects eutectic material and enables fresh copper to come into contact with the aluminium.

Support for this hypothesis is available from experiments carried out on the bonding of longitudinal sections of fibre-reinforced alloy. Here we used a copper foil sandwiched between two aluminium foils in order to promote the development of the bond. Figure 7 is an SEM picture of the bond produced at 550°C for 30 minutes; arrows mark the bond line. A good degree of bonding has taken place, whilst there is no copper and very little intermetallic phase present. Another major difference in microstructure compared with figure 6 is that appreciable quantities of a light phase occur between the fibres. EPMA identified this phase as the eutectic mixture, $\text{CuAl}_2 + \text{Al}$. Thus the presence of the aluminium foils has favoured the solution of the copper and the production of the eutectic. The eutectic has then been rejected from the interface under the applied pressure, much of it being forced along pores and interstices between the fibres. As shown in figure 5 such porosity seems to be a common feature of composites manufactured by the liquid metal infiltration route. Another point worth mentioning is that the stress vs. time profile for this specimen resembled figure 1a rather than figure 1b.

In conclusion, it has been shown that the use of a thin copper interlayer, combined with appropriate conditions of pressure, temperature and time can produce satisfactory bonds between aluminium alloy components. If a poor joint does occur it can be attributed to layers of brittle intermetallic adjacent to the bond line, which then crack on cooling the joint from the bonding temperature.

When applying this technique to fibre-reinforced aluminium alloys the situation is rather more complex and conditions found suitable for just the metal may not work when fibres are present. In particular, the fibres may affect the manner in which the two components are allowed to meet under pressure, with the result that a brittle intermetallic phase may remain at the bond line. We have demonstrated in this paper that the use of a more complex interlayer system can overcome the problem.

REFERENCES.

- (1) Kinloch, A. J., J. Mat. Sci 15 (1980), 2141-2166
- (2) Haynes, C. W., Metal Progress, March 1969, 83-86
- (3) Dunford, D. V., Partridge, P. G., "Superplasticity in Aerospace - Aluminium", Proc. of an International Conference, Cranfield Institute of Technology U.K., July 1985, p257
- (4) Scott, V.D., Love, G., "Quantitative Electron-Probe Microanalysis", Ellis Horwood Ltd, 1983, p244

Acknowledgements.

To the SERC and MOD for financial support, and to Mr H. G. Pullin and Mr. J. Manson for assistance with experimental aspects.

Figure 1a : Stress vs. Time profile for unreinforced metal.

Figure 1b : Stress vs. Time profile for reinforced metal.

Figure 2. Sample bonded for 30 minutes at 510°C (x400).

Figure 3. Samples bonded for 60 mins at 510°C (x 400).

Figure 4. Sample bonded for 60 mins at 525°C (x 1000).

Figure 5. Microstructure of reinforced metal (x400).

Figure 6. Reinforced sample bonded 30 mins at 525°C (x1000).

Figure 7. Backscattered SEM of sample bonded at 550°C for 30 mins with Cu and Al foils(x1500).